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**Mentoring as a Relational Principle of
Raising Young Leaders: An Exegetical
Study of 2 Timothy 2:2 in the Nigerian
Baptist Context**

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Abstract

Leadership development in Nigerian churches continues to face challenges related to succession, generational continuity, and an overreliance on formal theological training that often neglects relational formation. The study examines mentoring as a relational principle for raising young leaders, drawing on an exegetical analysis of 2 Timothy 2:2 within the Nigerian Baptist context. Using biblical-theological reflection and contextual analysis, the study explores the Pauline model of leadership transmission and its relevance for contemporary ministry. The findings reveal that mentoring in 2 Timothy 2:2 is intentional, relational, and generational, integrating character formation with leadership competence through life-on-life discipleship. The study further shows that while the Nigerian Baptist Convention benefits from strong institutional structures and communal cultural resources, hierarchical ministry patterns and limited intentional mentoring hinder the effective reproduction of leadership. It concludes that mentoring is a theological imperative for sustainable leadership development and recommends integrating structured mentoring systems, intergenerational engagement, and

relational discipleship into church and theological education practices.

Keywords: Mentoring, Relational Leadership, Leadership Development, 2 Timothy 2:2, Nigerian Baptist Convention

Introduction

Leadership development continues to occupy a central place in ecclesial life and mission, particularly within rapidly expanding Christian contexts (Banks & Ledbetter, 2004; Malphrus, 2003). In Nigeria, the growth of the church has not always been matched by corresponding depth in leadership formation, resulting in persistent challenges related to succession, ministerial effectiveness, and generational continuity. While the Nigerian Baptist Convention (NBC) has made significant contributions through theological education and institutional expansion, challenges related to leadership succession, ministerial effectiveness, and generational continuity persist.

One major factor contributing to these challenges is the insufficient emphasis on mentoring as a relational process of leadership formation. Relationships do not flourish by accident. They require attention and intentionality (Packiam, 2022). Contemporary approaches to leadership development often prioritise formal training and institutional frameworks, sometimes at the expense of relational dynamics. However, biblical leadership is fundamentally relational, rooted in life-on-life investment and discipleship.

The apostolic instruction in 2 Timothy 2:2 provides a compelling framework for understanding mentoring as a means of leadership reproduction. The text emphasises the intentional transmission of truth and responsibility across multiple generations of leaders. This study explores mentoring as a relational principle for raising young leaders, with particular attention to its theological foundation, exegetical basis, and practical implications within the Nigerian Baptist context.

The central thesis of this paper is that mentoring, as articulated in 2 Timothy 2:2, constitutes a theological and relational framework for the reproduction of leadership that, when intentionally applied within the Nigerian Baptist Convention, offers a sustainable model for raising competent and faithful young leaders. The pursuit of deep, intimate relationships is a lifelong quest for any pastor who wants to last in ministry and emerge as truly and fully human beings. No matter how good a pastor

is at preaching or other ministerial responsibilities, they are nothing without being intentional about their intimate relationships (Packiam, 2022).

Conceptual and Theoretical Framework

1. ***Mentoring as a Leadership Development Process:*** According to Packiam (2022), mentoring is an asymmetrical relationship in which an experienced individual invests in or cares for a less experienced person. It is widely understood as a developmental and relational process in which a more experienced individual intentionally invests in the growth of a less experienced person by providing guidance, support, and knowledge (Kram, 1985; Clutterbuck, 2004). According to George (2014), mentoring involves a more experienced individual tutoring, raising, teaching, and training a less experienced person. Within Christian contexts, mentoring extends beyond skill acquisition to encompass spiritual formation, character development, and vocational discernment (Stanley & Clinton, 1992). Mentoring can take various forms, including formal programs, informal relationships, peer mentoring, group mentoring, and spiritual direction. Regardless of its form, the defining characteristic of mentoring is relational engagement aimed at holistic development. Mentoring is at its best when the time spent is unstructured leisure rather than hours spent working together (Packiam, 2022).
2. ***Relational Leadership Theory:*** Relational leadership theory emphasises that leadership effectiveness is fundamentally rooted in the quality of relationships between leaders and followers (Uhl-Bien, 2006). Rather than prioritising hierarchical authority, this perspective foregrounds trust, mutual engagement, and interpersonal influence as the basis of leadership practice (Breedt & Niemandt, 2013; Dariya, 2024). This approach resonates strongly with biblical models of leadership, which are inherently communal and relational in orientation (Banks & Ledbetter, 2004). Leader-Member Exchange (LMX) theory also highlights the importance of high-quality relationships between leaders and followers (Graen & Uhl-Bien, 1995). When hostility and antagonism characterise a leader-follower relationship, it drastically reduces the effectiveness of both. No leader-follower relationship can be effective without a cordial relationship

(Oyedemi, 2018). Relationally intelligent leaders move away from a positional mindset to a mindset of relational authority. Relational leadership theory suggests that (1) leadership is a function, (2) leadership is contextual, (3) leadership is shared interdependency, (4) leadership is a relationship, and (5) leadership is balance (Breedt & Niemandt, 2013).

3. ***Transformational and Social Learning Perspectives:*** Transformational leadership theory identifies individualised consideration as a key dimension of effective leadership, in which the leader listens carefully to followers' needs and acts to meet them (Bass & Riggio, 2006; Stanko, 2012). Mentoring embodies this dimension by providing personalised attention and development opportunities. Bandura's (1977) social learning theory further supports mentoring by emphasising learning through observation, imitation, and modelling. Mentoring relationships create environments where emerging leaders can observe and internalise leadership behaviours.

Exegetical Analysis of 2 Timothy 2:2

1. ***Historical and Literary Context:*** Paul had a constellation of relationships that surrounded and shaped his life and ministry. Beginning with Ananias, Barnabas, Silas, Silvanus, Timothy, Epaphras, Peter, James, Luke, Priscilla and Aquila, Philemon, and Onesimus, among others (Packiam, 2022). The pastoral epistles were written in a context of doctrinal challenges and leadership transition. Paul, nearing the end of his ministry, writes to Timothy to ensure the continuity of sound teaching and effective leadership (Towner, 2006). The epistle reflects a concern for safeguarding the gospel and establishing reliable leadership structures.
2. ***Textual Analysis:*** 2 Timothy 2:2 states, "And what you have heard from me through many witnesses entrust to faithful people who will be able to teach others also" (NRSV). While commenting on the phrases "*heard from me,*" "*presence of many witnesses,*" and "*faithful men who will be able to teach others,*" in the text, MacArthur (2006) explains that during Timothy's many years of close association with Paul, he had heard divine truth which God had revealed through the apostles. Moreover, men like Silas, Barnabas, and Luke, and many others in the churches, could attest to the divine authenticity of Paul's teaching. He needed to

remind Timothy in light of the many defections at Ephesus (1 Timothy 1:15). Timothy was to take the divine revelation he had learned from Paul and teach it to other faithful men – men with proven spiritual character and giftedness, men who would in turn pass on those truths to another generation. From Paul, to Timothy, to faithful men, to others, encompasses 4 generations of godly leaders. That process of spiritual reproduction which began in the early church is to continue until the Lord returns. The imperative *entrust* in 2 Timothy 2:2 conveys the notion of intentional transmission and responsible stewardship of apostolic teaching (Towner, 2006). Paul’s instruction outlines a multi-generational framework of leadership reproduction – moving from himself to Timothy, to faithful individuals, and ultimately to others – thereby establishing a pattern of continuity grounded in both character and competence. This progression underscores that leadership development in the early church was neither incidental nor institutional, but relational and deliberate.

3. **Theological Implications:** This passage presents mentoring as:
- **Relational:** Mentoring is a relationship between partners and fellow workers, characterized by mutual respect and confidence (Breedt & Niemandt, 2013).
 - **Intentional:** Mentoring relationships do not flourish by accident. They require attention and intentionality. Ministry is full of demands; hence, the pastor must be intentional about their mentoring relationships (Packiam, 2022).
 - **Reproductive:** Mentoring requires the wisdom of those who have come before us, those who see what is in us and what lies ahead of us, and summon us to the journey anyway for the sake of ministerial multiplication (Packiam, 2022).

This model establishes mentoring as a theological mandate for leadership development within the church. Stanley (2019) explains that it is our duty to choose and teach committed young people to follow in the footsteps that we have learned so that they, too, can serve the Lord. In that way, we ensure that the work will continue even when we are gone – and that is essential for Christian ministry.

Mentoring in Biblical Theology

Mentoring is deeply embedded in biblical narratives. The relationship between Moses and Joshua (Exodus 24:13), Elijah and Elisha (2 Kings 2), and Jesus and His disciples (Mark 3:14) all demonstrate the importance of relational leadership formation. Paul's relationship with Timothy further exemplifies intentional mentoring within the early church (Phil. 2:22). Nouwen (1989) argues that: (1) Leadership becomes relational and communal, not individualistic. The leader serves with others, not above them, (2) Christian leadership is "downward mobility" – a movement toward the cross, where leadership is expressed through surrender rather than control, and (3) Christian leadership is fundamentally relational and grounded in service rather than power. Bonhoeffer (1954) similarly emphasizes the communal nature of Christian formation, highlighting the importance of shared life in discipleship. These perspectives affirm that mentoring is central to the biblical understanding of leadership.

Mentoring and Leadership Development in the Nigerian Baptist Context

1. ***Contextual Overview and Review:*** The Nigerian Baptist Convention has experienced significant growth over the past few decades, marked by increased membership, institutional expansion, and mission engagement. However, this growth has also exposed challenges related to leadership development and succession. One of these challenges is the nature of succession in the multi-staff ministry. Olawuyi James (2019) explains that the nature of multi-staff ministry in the Nigerian Baptist Convention is unique. While some churches practice associate ministers' succession when the senior pastor leaves, others practice non-succession multi-staff ministry. Niyi-Ojo (2019) argues that the senior pastor has the responsibility to mentor his pastoral team members by nurturing and developing them. Meanwhile, the writer argues that there can be no effective leader-follower relationship in the multi-staff ministry, whether to nurture and develop followers, or to succeed the leaders, without a cordial relationship between the senior pastor and other members of the pastoral team. In the Nigerian Baptist context, multi-staff ministry is both positional and hierarchical because most theological institutions in Africa foster a fierce spirit of competition among students (Janvier & Thaba, 1997). In other words, while all pastors are equal in calling, the senior pastor is superior in role.

Therefore, pastors need to understand that multi-staff ministry is neither competitive nor contentious, but rather collaborative (James, 2019). To the writer, there is a sharp contradiction in the arguments that multi-staff ministry in Nigerian Baptist Convention churches is both positional and hierarchical, and that pastors need to understand that it is neither competitive nor contentious but rather collaborative. Positional and hierarchical leadership mentalities naturally promote competition and contention. If multi-staff ministry in the Nigerian Baptist Convention churches is to be collaborative, we have to review the positional and hierarchical mindsets that underpin the practice. Adapting the relational leadership theory argued by Breedt & Niemandt (2013) to aid mentoring and leadership development in the Nigerian Baptist Convention churches, the writer argues that the Nigerian Baptist Convention must treat multi-staff ministry as:

- a. ***Contextual:*** Not only who one is, but also when and where matter in practising multi-staff ministry. Pastors need to develop awareness and the ability to adapt to context. In other words, pastors participating in multi-staff ministry must have contextual intelligence and adaptive capacity to succeed in the Nigerian Baptist Convention's multi-staff ministry.
- b. ***Shared Interdependency:*** The Body metaphor of Romans 12 has been used to illustrate the interrelatedness of members of the Christian community. Breedt & Niemandt (2013) call it an unfolding leadership that unfolds within an organically functioning body. Any part of the body can take on a leadership role depending on the body's needs, but no leadership function is designed to operate alone. Similarly, Ephesians 4 outlines different functions in the body to ensure the leadership team represents a well-functioning body; their leadership functions include the apostolic, prophetic, evangelical, pastoral and teaching teams. The shared interdependence in the passage reflects the unity of the body of Christ amid diversity. The writer argues that while the church pastor, popularly known as the senior pastor in a typical Nigerian Baptist church practising multi-staff ministry, may serve as the coordinating or lead pastor, all pastors should be interdependent in the church's pastoral ministry. Pastors in the multi-staff ministry of the same church should see one another as companions, where

no one tries to take another's role, but each carries one another's burden as individuals play their roles. For these pastors, their relationships are mutual, symmetrical in power, even if there are differences in their giftedness and functions (Packiam, 2022). Hence, every member of the pastoral team will learn to appreciate the uniqueness each brings to the ministerial relationship. This working relationship will aid mentoring and leadership development in the team.

- c. ***Relationships:*** Multi-staff ministry is relationships between partners and fellow ministers. The theological significance of life in the Trinity and the description of the church as imitating the Trinity should guide the relationships among pastors in a multi-staff ministry. Through our connection with Christ, we have the responsibility and privilege of reflecting the nature of the Triune God. The writer argues that multi-staff ministry, as a mission of the church, is far more about God and who God is than about any individual pastor on the team and what they do. The 'top-down' hierarchical structure of a typical Nigerian Baptist church multi-staff ministry immediately suggests a person under the authority and control of another minister within the same church. The multi-staff pastoral ministry of the church should be a constellation of voices, a fellowship of the pastorate, and a mutual relationship in which all pastors on the team get along well and are accountable to one another (Packiam, 2022). Basic relationships of staff in a multi-staff context, according to Samson Adedokun (2019), are: (1) the vertical relationship, (2) the horizontal relationship, and (3) the ministry relation. While the vertical relationship is the individual's relationship with God, the horizontal relationship is the interaction between members of the pastoral team, and the ministry relationship addresses the interface between members of the multi-staff ministry, including: a heart connection (do members of the pastoral team have the same passion?), a head connection (do they hold the same point of view?), and a hand connection (are they working as partners?).

Treating the multi-staff ministry of a typical Nigerian Baptist church as contextual, shared interdependency, and relationships will address the other various challenges surrounding mentoring

and hindering effective leadership reproduction and sustainability in the Nigerian Baptist context, including: limited intentional mentoring, overreliance on formal theological education, generational gaps between the leader and followers in the pastoral team, and institutional rather than relational approaches to leadership, among others.

2. ***Cultural Considerations:*** Cultural considerations are the flip side of mentoring and leadership development in the Nigerian Baptist context. The African communal worldview provides a fertile context for mentoring, as it traditionally emphasises interdependence, shared responsibility, and the generational transmission of values (Janvier & Thaba, 1997). Janvier & Thaba (1997) explain that the overall design of African traditional leadership lends itself naturally to a good biblical leadership style. Both the Bible and African culture emphasise the importance of character formation for leaders. Culturally, in Africa, a leader is not only expected to possess outstanding qualities but also to demonstrate them. For example, an African man must not only marry but also control his family in accordance with societal norms. Just as the biblical role of elders is spiritual and communal, the role of an African traditional elder in the community is to make decisions, and every member of the community adheres to them without objection. In most African homes, the father is the head of the family. The father, as the head of the family, is both biblical and traditional. However, contemporary socio-cultural shifts, including urbanization and increasing individualism, have weakened these relational structures, thereby necessitating more intentional approaches to mentoring within the church. Therefore, because pastoral ministry takes a toll on the pastors' families, pastors must have good relationships with their spouses and children to mentor and develop their families. If pastors make their ministry tough on their families, it will make everything miserable for them. The pastors' families love them, not because of how well they preach, sing, lead children's ministry, or recruit volunteers, but because of who they are (Packiam, 2022). In other words, who the pastor is, not necessarily what they do, is what matters to their spouses and children, and this is what will make mentoring and leadership development of the pastors' families successful.

Mentoring as a Relational Principle for Raising Young Leaders

Mentoring serves as a foundational relational principle for leadership development in several ways:

1. **Intentional Leadership Formation:** Mentoring provides a structured yet relational pathway for identifying and developing emerging leaders. These, according to Parsley (2012), include:
 - **Coaching for life:** Spending time with a young person so the mentor can provide feedback and coaching across different phases of life creates a trusting relationship. The goal of mentoring is to help young people learn not just from their mistakes but also from the mentor's. Coaching is teaching skills and character training for success.
 - **Caring for needs:** Coming to the aid of a person in crisis or with a need that can only be met by someone older and wiser helps a young person feel safe. Identifying their needs even before they do, with compassion and a solution, creates a bond that is hard to break. Love and care are the currency of mentorship.
 - **Challenging for improvement:** Zeroing in on the areas of a young person's life that they really struggle with and pushing them to change and achieve is one of the greatest contributions a mentor can make. Course correction must be done consistently to protect a young person from a failure that is too great, but it also includes encouraging them to learn from their failures and bounce back.
 - **Cheering for confidence:** young people need someone who will cheer them on and tell them that they can do it. Building confidence seasoned with humility is one of the primary goals for mentors who want to see a young person succeed. Cheering means identifying strengths, not just pointing out weaknesses. It is positive reinforcement that balances out the correction and invests in the sometimes-vulnerable psyche of a young person.
2. **Character and Competence Development:** Character failure in leadership occurs when the leader does not allow Christ to lead them in love, humility, and community (Nouwen, 1989). Character is the only secure foundation of any form of leadership. It is indispensable to credibility, and credibility is essential to leadership (Mohler, 2012). Hence, the mentor will raise young leaders to submit to Christ and allow Christ to lead them in love, humility, and community. Competence

development is the acquisition of skills and training for expertise. Competence in pastoral ministry is imperative and requires a total commitment and enthusiasm (Idowu, 2017). According to Ademola Ishola (2021), competence in pastoral ministry requires a commitment to team building, conflict management, long-range planning, investing in the next generation, providing a strong organisational structure, and bringing innovation to the worship of God. Thus, the emphasis on faithfulness and teaching ability in 2 Timothy 2:2 highlights the integration of spiritual maturity and leadership skills.

3. **Leadership Multiplication:** Mentoring fosters a multiplication mindset, ensuring that leadership development extends beyond individual leaders to future generations. According to Oswald Sanders (1967), the true test of leadership is the organisation's health when the leader is gone. Leadership multiplication requires a service inspired by God and built on spiritual principles. It will survive the shock of leadership change. People are always God's greatest gifts, and Jesus' greatest endowment to the church was the gift of twelve people He trained and empowered for leadership. Leaders should mentor more people so that their departures create space for their mentees to emerge and develop. In other words, leaders must multiply themselves by developing younger leaders, giving them full play and adequate outlet for their abilities.

Conclusion

This study has argued that mentoring, as articulated in 2 Timothy 2:2, is not merely a supportive ministry activity but a theological and relational imperative for sustainable leadership development. The Pauline model presents a clear pattern of intentional transmission, where truth, character, and responsibility are entrusted across successive generations of faithful leaders. Such a model underscores that leadership in the church is inherently relational, deeply rooted in life-on-life discipleship, and oriented toward multiplication rather than mere maintenance.

Within the Nigerian Baptist context, the need to recover and prioritise this relational paradigm is both urgent and strategic. While the Nigerian Baptist Convention has made commendable strides in institutional and theological training, the persistence of leadership gaps, succession challenges, and generational discontinuities reveals the limitations of approaches that

underemphasize mentoring relationships. This study has demonstrated that effective leadership formation cannot be divorced from intentional, relational investment in emerging leaders.

The integration of relational theory, transformational leadership insights, and social learning perspectives further reinforces the biblical mandate of mentoring. These frameworks collectively affirm that leadership effectiveness is cultivated through trust-based relationships, modelled behaviour, and individualised development. In this regard, mentoring serves as a bridge between theological knowledge and practical ministry competence, and between current leadership and future sustainability.

Moreover, the Nigerian cultural context – with its strong communal heritage – provides a fertile ground for mentoring to thrive if intentionally harnessed. However, contemporary challenges such as individualism, hierarchical rigidity, and institutional dominance must be critically addressed. Reframing multi-staff ministry as a relational, interdependent, and collaborative enterprise is essential to fostering environments in which mentoring can flourish organically and effectively.

Practically, this study calls for a deliberate shift from programmatic leadership development to relational discipleship models. Structured mentoring systems, intentional intergenerational engagement, and the integration of mentoring into theological education are necessary steps toward embedding this principle within the life of the church. Senior leaders, in particular, bear the responsibility for modelling mentoring relationships that prioritise character formation, competence development, and leadership multiplication.

Ultimately, the enduring strength of the church lies not in its structures but in its people – faithful men and women who are equipped, entrusted, and empowered to teach others as well. Mentoring, therefore, is the divinely ordained means by which leadership continuity is secured and the mission of the church is advanced. As Nigerian Baptist churches embrace mentoring as a central relational principle, they position themselves to raise a new generation of leaders who are spiritually grounded, relationally intelligent, and missionally effective.

Recommendations

In light of these findings, this study recommends the intentional development of structured mentoring systems within the Nigerian Baptist

churches. Such systems should be complemented by integrating mentoring into theological education and deliberately cultivating intergenerational relationships. These strategies are essential for fostering leadership continuity and ensuring the sustainable transmission of ministerial values and competencies.

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